

Council on Library and Information Resources

ANNUAL REPORT July 1, 2016–June 30, 2017

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT: From Diversity, Convergence

Early this century a new, interdisciplinary field of study was inaugurated, called sustainability science. This field incorporates the knowledge and research gained through traditionally scientific disciplines with that gained from the social sciences and humanities to more deeply and coherently inform our policies and help model our behaviors to become better stewards of a planet that already is succumbing to potentially catastrophic climate shifts.

In reading the research and background, it struck me that CLIR has adopted over the last decade an

approach to our projects and programs that correlates closely with the tenets and goals of this fresh field of inquiry. Think of academic information as a virtual ecosystem. Our endeavors are guided by principles and desired results that map comfortably upon sustainability science—principles that include diversity, convergence, and equality.

We have expanded significantly into interdisciplinary research. Our data curation postdoctoral fellows program, for example, now spans more than 25 disciplines in the sciences, social sciences, and humanities as our fellows manage, secure, preserve, and make accessible hundreds of instances of big data. The Cataloging Hidden Collections program and its successor, Digitizing Hidden Collections, have brought to CLIR a far more diverse institutional constituency, now including libraries, archives, museums, religious centers, historical societies,

film societies, and a spectrum of media. The Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME) provides services to the academic leaders and institutions in the Middle East and North Africa, and represents an exciting geographic expansion to our portfolio.

Such diversity of perspectives, interests, cultural legacy, and subject matter is not an end in itself, but a means to broaden the scope of CLIR's services in order to strengthen convergence, in this case the process of coming together and working inter-dependently, using shared resources, extensible applications, interoperable digital platforms, and easily migrated and reusable data. Trusted confluence at a global scale frames all of our current work.

And from diversity and convergence: equality. Our fundamental aspiration is to provide a wealth of information and services that are open, accessible to all, and maintained through community involvement. This knowledge is organized and continually enriched to invigorate our capacity to understand this complex world, to become better stewards of its invaluable virtual resources, and to assure, as best we can, that this knowledge is both integral to and informs the essential responsibility of any generation: a sustainable future.

—Charles Henry

CLIR is dedicated to building a rich and coherent information environment. We believe the future of learning depends on the preservation, organization, and accessibility of information. We foster collaboration by investing in cross-disciplinary intellectual leadership, strategic programs, and professional development opportunities.

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NEW INITIATIVES: DIGITAL LIBRARY OF THE MIDDLE EAST

Working to federate Middle Eastern collections from around the world, creating a publicly accessible, interoperable digital library of cultural material.

In response to the tragic displacement of people, loss of life in conflict zones, and ongoing threats to the cultural heritage of the Middle East, the Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME) aims to create an internationally shared digital inventory of cultural artifacts that includes detailed and culturally nuanced descriptions and images. Records from the DLME will be publicly available to encourage scholarly discoveries and greater appreciation of the region's rich heritage and living peoples, while helping safeguard important expressions of our cultural commonwealth and shared humanity.

Formal planning for the DLME launched in July 2016, with a grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to support exploratory research, community building, and technical prototyping. In May 2017, the Whiting Foundation awarded CLIR \$170,000 to design, implement, and launch a DLME proof of concept in early 2018.

Read more at <https://dlme.clir.org/>

Among the items available through the DLME prototype is this belt ornament in the form of a bird demon from the collection of the Metropolitan Museum of Art. Urartu, bronze, ca. late 8th – 7th century B.C. Gift of Norbert Schimmel Trust, 1989.

NEW INITIATIVES: RECORDINGS AT RISK

Supporting professionals to act against the threat of media degradation and obsolescence

Much of the world's audiovisual archives exist on decaying carriers and require urgent intervention if they are to survive. Our audio heritage is held by thousands of institutions that bear responsibility for saving our audiovisual legacy. Launched in October 2016 with support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, Recordings at Risk is a national regrantee program to support the preservation of rare and unique audio and audiovisual content of high scholarly value through digital reformatting. The program will run four competitions between January 2017 and September 2018 awarding a total of \$2.3 million.

[Seven institutions](#) received Recordings at Risk grants for audio digitization in the program's first round of awards, announced April 28, 2017.

Read more at <https://www.clir.org/recordings-at-risk/>.

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The Digital Library Federation (DLF) encompasses a group of 159 networked member institutions and a robust community of practice—advancing research, learning, social justice, and the public good through the creative design and wise application of library technologies. DLF connects CLIR’s vision and research agenda with its active practitioner network.

The annual Forum is DLF's signature event. It serves as an essential meeting place for digital library, archives, and museum practitioners from member institutions and beyond. Here, the DLF community celebrates successes, learns from mistakes, sets grassroots agendas, and organizes for action.

I left the Forum with much more than a notebook full of questions, ideas, and resources to investigate; I left with a better sense of who I want to be as an LIS professional and a renewed understanding of why we do what we do.

–Margaret Huang, Digital Archivist
Philadelphia Museum of Art
2016 ARL+DLF Fellowship Recipient

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Stacie Williams, of Case Western University, opened the 2016 Forum in Milwaukee with a keynote drawing on her work in labor issues. The Forum and its affiliated events—DLF Liberal Arts College Preconference and NDSA Digital Preservation 2016—drew some 700 people. DLF fellowships enabled 17 people from 13 institutions to attend.

Read more at <https://www.diglib.org/dlf-events/2016forum/>

DLF more than **doubled the number of Working Groups**, which enable grassroots action across boundaries. New working groups were formed for Government Records, Mentors, Labor in Digital Libraries, Born-Digital Access, and Metadata Support.

\$ DLF **awarded 10 Cross-Pollinator Awards**, funding individuals to take part in conferences they might not otherwise attend. The awards are intended to encourage conversation and collaboration across professional communities.

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DLF launched the first **Endangered Data Week** (EDW) in April 2017. Launched to raise awareness of the threats to publicly available data, EDW held more than 50 activities in the United States, Spain, and Australia.

DLF published a **DLF Organizers' Toolkit**, a shared resource to improve documentation of evolving community norms, contribute to best practice and institutional memory, and support those wishing to use DLF to advance the field.

In May, DLF welcomed the 2017 **e-Research Network (eRN)** cohort of 42 people from 14 institutions. The eRN brings together teams from research-supporting libraries to strengthen and advance their data services and digital scholarship roles. **The 2016 eRN cohort** concluded its work in November with a capstone meeting at the Forum.

In July 2016, DLF awarded the first **Community/Capacity Awards** to the Biodiversity Heritage Library and the American Archive of Public Broadcasting.

DIGITIZING HIDDEN SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

The Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives program supports the digitization of original sources of high scholarly and community value, while enhancing the emerging global digital research environment in ways that support new kinds of scholarship for the long term.

In 2016, CLIR awarded grants to **17 projects** totaling **\$4,008,407** and **involving 34 institutions**. 12% of applications were funded.

A six-part webinar series, *Strategies for Advancing Hidden Collections*, documenting lessons learned by recipients of previous cataloging grants, was offered in January and February 2017.

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2016 Awards, Participating Institutions

By geographic region

- Northeast/Mid-Atlantic
- Southeast
- Midwest
- Southwest
- West

By type of institution

- University Library or Archive
- Independent Archive
- Liberal Arts College Library or Archive
- Museum
- Public/Government Library or Archive

A list of funded projects is at <https://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/funded-projects/#2016>

A few examples of the resources made available by 2016 Hidden Collections awardees

Clockwise: [Digitizing the New York Quilt Project](#); [The Woman Behind the Camera: Home Movies and Amateur Film by Women, 1925–1997](#); [Digitizing Southern California Water Resources](#); [Out Front: 60 Years of LGBTQ Political Graphics at ONE Archives](#); [Avian Archives of Iowa Online](#).

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM

Postdoctoral Fellowships build leadership capacity while enabling libraries and other hosts to explore new roles and ways of tackling massive systemic challenges facing the future of scholarly communication.

In May 2017, CLIR named **12 new fellows for 2017-2019**. Sixteen fellows continued from 2016. These **28 fellows are working at 25 institutions**.

To date, CLIR has supported **166 fellows**.

Since 2014, CLIR has provided microgrants to Fellows in Data Curation. Microgrants promote collaborative research on problems shared across institutions that benefits the broader scholarly and professional communities. Fellows develop ideas in collaboration with other fellows and with input from scholars and experts in relevant areas.

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Fellows active in 2016–2017

By discipline

- Humanities
- Social Sciences
- Natural Sciences

By funding source

- The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
- Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
- Host partners

A list of current and previous fellows is at <https://www.clir.org/fellowships/postdoc/fellowsupdate/>

IMPACTS: Postdoctoral Fellows in Data Curation

Insights

With support from a 2017 fellowship microgrant, three postdoctoral fellows in medieval studies are collaborating with two mentors on [Labeculae Vivae: Building a Reference Library of Stains for Researching Medieval Manuscripts](#) (#StainAlive). Fellows are gathering scientific data drawn from stains found on parchment, paper, and bindings in medieval manuscripts produced between 500 and 1500. Using multispectral imaging of some 50 manuscripts from 5 repositories and control samples created by the fellows, the data will afford researchers, conservators, librarians, and the public new insights about the material makeup of medieval manuscripts and their uses.

Perspective

From Izul Zulkarnain and, before him, our fellow Kyle Parry, I learned to be more critical of metadata structures and how they impact representation. In the digital space we are bounded by the technologies and data structures that we build, and we build our own lenses into those structures, either consciously or unconsciously. Through the work with Izul, I saw how those structures perpetuate Western viewpoints and how we can attempt to create more expansive and inclusive structures that allow greater access to our digital assets and projects by non-English speaking users. I will always approach my work with this critical lens as a result of my work with Izul and Kyle.

–Supervisor Nora Dimmock

Practice

Mason Scott Thompson is a 2016–2018 Postdoctoral Fellow at the U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID). He is helping the agency align government practices with current academic best practices for managing, curating, and protecting heterogeneous data, and is advising on the use of best practice digital infrastructure. He provides project leadership on enterprise data initiatives, such as the long-term management and curation of USAID data, master data management, data interoperability and exchange, and data sharing and publication. He also works closely on development of the Agency's central digital repository, the [Development Data Library](#).

MELLON FELLOWSHIPS FOR DISSERTATION RESEARCH IN ORIGINAL SOURCES

Mellon Fellowships encourage research with and innovative uses of original sources by junior scholars in the humanities and related social sciences. Researchers are encouraged to think across disciplinary lines, to consider the formation and evolution of collections, and to recognize the integral role archivists play in both the history and contemporary act of knowledge production.

The work of the CLIR Mellon Fellows suggests that . . . archives exist as sites where interdisciplinary conversations should take place, where the digital histories and living ritual spaces can flourish, and where censored words can speak and muted bodies can be personalized yet again.

–Nicole Ferraiolo and R. A. Kashanipour

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17 awardees were [named](#) in April 2017.

Since 2002, the program has supported **227 fellows** for research at **1,200 sites** in **76 countries**.

Read more at

<https://www.clir.org/fellowships/mellon/>

2016 Mellon Fellow Elham Bahktary conducted his research at the Library of Congress.

LEADING CHANGE INSTITUTE

The Leading Change Institute (LCI) is designed for leaders in higher education, including CIOs, librarians, information technology professionals, and administrators, who want to work collaboratively to promote and initiate change on critical issues affecting the academy. Sponsored jointly with EDUCAUSE, the program provides an intensive, wide-scope professional development opportunity.

The skills necessary to navigate the complexities of individual colleges and universities are multifaceted, and probably can't be learned in abstraction. LCI builds its programming around giving participants opportunities to participate in scenario creation and role playing—and to practice these skills in environments of uncertainty and ambiguity.

—Joshua Kim, 2017 LCI Participant

33 individuals participated in the 2017 LCI, led by deans Joanne Kossuth and Elliott Shore, in Washington, DC, June 11–16.

To date, the program has graduated **700 alumni** from a broad range of domestic and international institutions of higher learning.

Read more and see alumni list at <https://leadingchangeinstitute.org/>

PUBLICATIONS

This year, CLIR published *The Open Data Imperative*, examining governmental agencies' plans to meet the federal mandate for public access to data and publications. CLIR also produced two program assessments. The first considers the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education and how to build on its legacy to support the use of digital technologies in liberal education.

The second assessment, *Keepers of Our Digital Future*, investigates the early impacts of the National Digital Stewardship Residency programs, to inform subsequent development of similar programs.

CLIR also published six editions of its bimonthly newsletter, *CLIR Issues*, and several blog posts in its *Re: Thinking* series.

AFFILIATES

CLIR continues to forge partnerships with selected organizations in pursuit of common goals. These partnerships offer us the opportunity to engage meaningfully with new constituencies and signify our commitment to the vision of interdependence—working together in ways that go well beyond collaboration or cooperation. In December 2016, CLIR and Axiell announced their affiliation. In March 2017, CLIR and Jisc announced their affiliation.

The logo for EDUCAUSE features the word "EDUCAUSE" in a bold, white, sans-serif font, centered within a dark red rectangular background.

Revenue and Expenses

As of June 30, 2017

Revenue

- Grants and contracts—84%
- Sponsors and members—9%
- Leading Change Institute—1%
- DLF registrations—2%
- Affiliates—3%
- Other income—1%

Expenses

- Programs—91%
- Fundraising and development—1%
- General administrative—8%

Statement of Financial Position

As of June 30, 2017

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total June 30, 2017
CURRENT ASSETS:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$723,947	\$5,597,732	\$6,321,679
Investments	233,466	306,304	539,770
Prepaid expenses	238,523	-	238,523
Accounts receivable	15,019	7,958,978	7,973,997
Total Current Assets	\$1,210,955	\$13,863,014	\$15,073,969
Furniture and equipment, net			
of accumulated depreciation	\$70,699	\$-	\$70,699
Other assets	29,915	-	29,915
TOTAL ASSETS	\$1,311,569	\$13,863,014	\$15,174,583
CURRENT LIABILITIES:			
Accounts payable	\$297,348	\$-	\$297,348
Capital lease payable	3,080	-	3,080
Accrued expenses	180,375	-	180,375
Total Current Liabilities	\$480,803	\$-	\$480,803
LONG-TERM LIABILITIES:			
Capital lease payable, net of current portion	\$3,870	\$-	3,870
TOTAL LIABILITIES	\$484,673	\$-	\$484,673
NET ASSETS	\$826,896	\$13,863,014	\$14,689,910
TOTAL LIABILITIES AND NET ASSETS	\$1,311,569	\$13,863,014	\$15,174,583

Sponsors and Funders

As of June 30, 2017

Alexander Street Press,
a ProQuest Company
Allegheny College
American University
Amherst College*
Arizona State University Libraries*
Atlanta University Center*
Auburn University Library
Bates College*
Baylor University*
Berea College
Bibliotheca Alexandrina+
Binghamton University*
Boston College*
Bowdoin College*
Brigham Young University
Brill
Brown University Library*
Bryn Mawr College Libraries*
Bucknell University*
California Digital Library*

California Polytechnic State University
California State University Channel Islands+
Carleton College
Carnegie Mellon University*
Carthage College
The Catholic University of America
Chemical Heritage Foundation+
The Claremont Colleges*
The Clark Art Institute
Clemson University+
Coalition for Networked Information*
Colby College*
Colgate University*
College of Charleston
College of the Holy Cross
Columbia University*
Connecticut College
Cornell University Libraries*
Dartmouth College*
Denison University*
DePauw University+

Dickinson College Library
Duke University*
Emory University*
Florida Atlantic University
Florida State University+
Folger Shakespeare Library
Franklin & Marshall College
Furman University*
The George Washington University*
Georgetown University*
Georgia Institute of Technology*
Georgia State University+
Getty Research Institute+
Grand Valley State University+
Grinnell College*
Hamilton College*
Harvard University*
Haverford College*
Illinois Wesleyan University+
Indiana University*
Internet Archive+

Iowa State University*
James Madison University+
Jisc*
Johns Hopkins University Libraries
Kenyon College*
Lafayette College*
Lake Forest College
Lehigh University*
Library of Congress*
Linfield College
Los Alamos National Laboratory+
Loyola Notre Dame Library
Macalester College+
Marquette University*
Massachusetts Institute of Technology*
McGill University+

Continued

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+DLF member only

Sponsors and Funders *(continued)*

As of June 30, 2017

McMaster University*
Metropolitan New York Library Council
(METRO)+
Miami University
Middle Tennessee State University*
Middlebury College*
Mississippi State University Libraries*
Montana State University*
Mount Holyoke College*
National Archives and Records
Administration+
National Library of Medicine*
New York Art Resources Consortium
(NYARC)+
New York Public Library*
New York University*
North Carolina State University Libraries*
Northeastern University*
Northwestern University Libraries*
Oberlin College*
Occidental College*

OCLC Research+
The Ohio State University*
Oregon State University Libraries*
Pacific Lutheran University
Pennsylvania State University*
Philadelphia Museum of Art+
Preservation Technologies
Princeton Theological Seminary+
Princeton University Library*
Purdue University Library*
Reed College*
Rhodes College*
Rice University*
Rockefeller University*
Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey
St. Lawrence University*
St. Olaf College*
Sewanee: The University of the South
Skidmore College
Smith College*
Smithsonian Institution*

Southern Methodist University*
Stanford University
Stony Brook University Libraries*
Swarthmore College*
Syracuse University*
Temple University Library*
Texas A&M*
Texas Tech*
Tufts University*
Tulane University
Union College
Université Laval
University of Alabama*
University of Alabama at Birmingham*
University at Albany*
University of Alberta*
University of Arizona Library*
University of Arkansas*
University of British Columbia*
University of California, Berkeley*
University of California, Irvine*

University of California, Los Angeles*
University of California, Riverside+
University of California, San Diego
Libraries*
University of California, Santa Barbara*
University of Chicago Library*
University of Cincinnati
University of Colorado at Boulder*
University of Delaware Library*
University of Denver*
University of Georgia Libraries*
University of Guelph*
University of Houston*
University of Illinois at Chicago*
University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign*

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Sponsors and Funders *(continued)*

As of June 30, 2017

University of Iowa Libraries*
University of Kansas*
University of Kentucky Libraries*
University of Manitoba+
University of Maryland at College Park*
University of Massachusetts Libraries
University of Miami*
University of Michigan*
University of Minnesota Libraries*
University of Nebraska-Lincoln*
University of New Mexico*
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*
University of North Carolina at Charlotte*
University of North Carolina at Greensboro*
University of North Texas*
University of Notre Dame*
University of Oklahoma Libraries
University of Oregon
University of Ottawa*
University of Pennsylvania*

University of Pittsburgh*
University of Richmond*
University of Rochester*
University of St. Thomas
University of San Francisco*
University of South Carolina*
University of South Florida
University of Southern California*
University of Tennessee*
University of Texas at Arlington*
University of Texas at Austin*
University of Toronto Library*
University of Utah*
University of Victoria
University of Virginia*
University of Washington*
University of Wisconsin-Madison*
University of Wyoming*
Ursinus College
Vanderbilt University
Vassar College Libraries*

Villanova University
Virginia Commonwealth University
Virginia Tech*
Wake Forest University*
Washington and Lee University Library*
Washington University in St. Louis*
Wellesley College
Wesleyan University
West Virginia University Libraries*
Whitman College*
Williams College Libraries*
Wilson College
Yale University Library*

Foundation and Institutional Support:

The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
Institute for Museum and Library Services
Library of Congress
Samuel H. Kress Foundation
Whiting Foundation

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